

D3.6

EMPOWER

deliverables

Deliverable title

Final Platform Release

Type

Document - Report

Dissemination level

PU - Public

Date

M30

Final platform release including improvements from field tests

Description

WP.3

Work Package. 3

Lead Beneficiary - UVEG

Final Platform Release

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable includes links to all the software components and hardware details necessary to successfully run the EMPOWER platform with all its games. It also links to related deliverables, where the description of the platform functionality is provided. It also includes a video that demonstrates how the platform works, with details of all the platform games.

Date	Version	Description	Authors
20.03.2024	0.1	First Draft	All EMPOWER partners

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#1. Introduction

The EMPOWER Platform is aimed at supporting the development of executive functions and emotional regulation in neurodevelopmental conditions. It has been co-designed by researchers of the EMPOWER consortium in close collaboration with neurodiverse populations and teachers.

A detailed description of the games included in the platform can be found in public deliverable D2.1, titled Report containing all the detailed contents of the platform, as well as on the project Website.

The EMPOWER project also included three pilot studies, one validation study, and a Randomized Clinical Trial to explore and test the efficacy of the platform. Those results and recommendations drawn from them are/will be summarised in D6.1 Report based on the pilot effectiveness, D6.2 Report of the validation studies, D6.3 Guideline for teachers, and D6.4 Report with the results from RCT. Additional information can be found in the scientific publications listed on the EMPOWER project website: <https://project-empower.eu>

#2. Downloadable files

The full version of the EMPOWER platform can be downloaded from this folder:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1y2ljzpe8vmKVINngpzA7A2vViU-63_v1?usp=drive_link

The folder includes:

- A version of the platform that can run connected to remote servers (Empower Application Remote.zip)
- A version of the platform that can run locally, which requires installing additional software on the server (Empower Application.zip)
- Server installation files and instructions (Server installation files and instructions.zip)
- A teacher app for Android tablets (Teacher app.apk)
- An app for a watch to measure heart rate (Wearable Application.apk)
- A video tutorial to show how to handle permissions for the wearable (Wearable_grant_access_permissions_tutorial.mp4)
- A video with a demonstration of the platform games (Empower project video.mp4)

Once the EMPOWER platform is installed, it is possible to test the application using this user and password:

- User: test@uv.es
- Password: test

#3. Recommended hardware

The EMPOWER platform requires a computer with a dedicated graphics card and Windows 11 installed. It is advisable to use a computer or laptop with a touchscreen, because the interaction for the user is easier and more natural, but it is not mandatory, because the user can use the keyboard and the mouse instead if they can do so. As a complementary device, the application allows the use of an Eye tracker connected to the computer and a wearable (watch) that is remotely connected to the computer through a local database.

The Eye tracker used is Tobii Pro Nano, which needs the corresponding drivers from the Tobii page installed locally on the computer. The wearable is a *Samsung Watch (X)* that needs an application installed that can be found in the above-mentioned folder.

The system is connected to a local MariaDB database, which needs to be installed on the computer used for the games. The installation process is described in Deliverable 3.5 in Annex 1.

Additionally, an Android tablet is needed to install the teacher application, where the teacher can create the sessions, receive feedback and recommendations, and follow the student's progress inside the tool. That application can be found in above-mentioned folder.

#3. Video demonstration

The above-mentioned folder contains a video (Empower project video.mp4) describing the EMPOWER platform functionality, with details about the purpose, design, and functioning of each EMPOWER game. It is recommended to view the video to gain a better understanding of the summarized functionality of the platform.

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Discover a few of our games

WORM

a game to promote Working Memory

REFLEX

a game to promote Cognitive Flexibility

MUSHROOM HUNTER

a game to promote Sustained Attention

RESTROOP

a game to promote Inhibitory Control

BEEHOLD

a game to promote Delayed Gratification

EMOTIFEST

a game to promote Emotional regulation

Co-funded by the European Union

Sustained Attention Game

Research

Sustained attention refers to the ability to maintain focus and engagement on a task over time, particularly in the conditions of monotony and repetition (Unsworth & Robinson, 2020).

Mushroom hunters
a game to promote Sustained attention

Mushroom hunters was developed on the work of Posner and Petersen (1990) and the Computerized Continuous Performance Task (CCPT; by Rosvold, Mirsky, Sarason, Bransome, & Beck, 1956).